

The dynamics of water-soluble organic matter in constructed soils of different composition

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Due to the increasing human impact on the environment, the study of urban soils, especially constructed soils, has become more important. One significant aspect of this research is the investigation of organic matter dynamics and composition including the water-soluble organic matter (WSOM), the most labile and biochemically active humic substances in soil.

Various transformation degrees of constructed soil profiles, with the obligatory presence of a surface recultivation-humus horizon named RAT are studied. The RAT horizon is usually formed by humus-accumulative masses (AU) of Haplic Chernozem (calcic). The content of total organic carbon (TOC) and the content of WSOM were determined by high-temperature catalytic combustion using a TOC-L CPN Shimadzu carbon analyzer. WSOM was eluted by cold and hot extraction. Statistical processing includes data descriptive statistics, as well as the calculation of the Spearman's correlation coefficient (r).

The TOC distribution in the constructed soil profile clearly has reflects the morphological bimodality of the soil profile. The highest TOC content occurs in surface horizons and buried humus layers of native soil. Anthropogenic surface horizons are characterized by a chaotic distribution of organic carbon, due to their genesis and the properties of filling materials, while the buried natural layers have shown a gradual decrease in organic carbon content. A strong negative correlation was found between TOC content and depth in Haplic Chernozems (Transportic, Technic) ($r=-0.75$) and moderate correlation in Urbic Technosols (Terric, Transportic) ($r=-0.64$), compared to a strong correlation inherent for Haplic Chernozem (calcic) ($r=-0.90$). WSOM content has shown a strong direct correlation with TOC content ($r = 0.85$). The profile WSOM distribution was similar to the TOC distribution and had inversions in the profile in case of buried natural profiles. The proportion of WSOM carbon in the TOC pool in all investigated soil was 2.5-5% and it was classified as "very high". In RAT horizon the WSOM carbon proportion was slightly lower ($2.59 \pm 0.67\%$), in the buried natural AU horizon was slightly higher ($3.44 \pm 1.52\%$), but this difference is absence statistically significant.

The composition and genesis of recultivation-humus RAT horizons were determining the specifics of the organic matter distribution in the profile. Despite the significant transformation, there is a significant pool of labile organic matter in constructed soil, including WSOM. This fact indicates the importance of WSOM in the soil formation processes and carbon cycling in urban ecosystems.

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